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Studies on Tartrato-Aquo Lead(II) and Its Substituted Derivatives

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BOBTELSKY and Graus¹ have reported the formation of insoluble lead tartrate $Pb_2C_4H_2O_6$ which transforms to $PbC_4H_4O_6$ at pH 8.5 and dissolves between pH 4 and 5. Panova² reported the increase in solubility of lead tartrate with increasing tartrate concentration at constant pH and was attributed to the formation of complex containing two tartrate ligands. A further survey of the literature reveals that there is no systematic study on the synthesis and characterization of lead(II) tartrate. As a part of our study on the synthesis of tartrate salts of different metal ions, we report the preparation and properties of lead(II) tartrate and a few of its derivatives in this communication.

Experimental

Analar (B.D.H.) quality chemicals were used. Lead(II) tartrate was prepared from an equimolar solution of lead nitrate and sodium potassium tartrate. The compound is almost insoluble in water, but is soluble in strong bases like sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide and also in aqueous ammonia, methyl, ethyl and other aliphatic amines. The evaporation of a saturated solution of lead tartrate in sodium hydroxide yields a compound of composition $Na PbT(OH) \cdot 4H_2O$, where T=tartrate ion. A similar compound, $K PbT(OH)$ is obtained from saturated solution in potassium hydroxide. These compounds are soluble in water and hydrolysed in dilute solution. The compounds similarly obtained from aqueous ammonia and amine solution are

insoluble in water and have composition $PbTR$, where R=ammonia or amine (Table 1).

The estimation of lead and nitrogen have been done respectively by sulphate and micro Kjeldahl's methods and that of tartrate by the procedure reported earlier³.

TABLE 1

Compounds	%Calculated			%Found		
	Pb	T	N	Pb	T	N
$PbT \cdot H_2O$	55.52	39.72	—	55.56	39.76	—
$K PbT(OH)$	50.41	35.99	—	51.82	34.86	—
$Na PbT(OH) \cdot 4H_2O$	44.39	31.67	—	45.39	32.12	—
$PbTNH_3$	55.69	39.77	3.76	54.78	37.89	3.43
$PbTNH_3CH_3$	53.67	38.32	3.62	52.32	37.58	3.21
$PbTN(CH_3)_3$	50.03	34.82	3.34	51.12	35.73	3.12
$PbTNH_3C_2H_5$	51.75	37.1	3.5	52.32	36.8	3.2
$PbTNH(C_2H_5)_3$	48.36	34.58	3.27	49.53	32.93	3.06
$PbTN(C_2H_5)_3$	45.37	32.45	3.07	47.21	30.36	2.89

The i.r. spectra of $PbT \cdot H_2O$, $PbT \cdot NH_3$ and $PbT \cdot N(CH_3)_3$ were taken in potassium bromide phase, and some of the absorption bands are collected in Table 2.

Discussion

In sodium potassium tartrate, one strong and one weak band are observed at 1620 cm^{-1} and 1455 cm^{-1} respectively which are due to symmetrical and antisymmetrical vibration of the carboxylate groups whereas in d-tartaric acid, the sharp band at 1750 cm^{-1} and 1097 cm^{-1} have been assigned to the free carboxylic acid group and C=O stretching frequency of secondary alcoholic group respectively⁴.

In $PbTH_2O$, $PbT \cdot NH_3$ and $PbTN(CH_3)_3$ strong bands are found at 1560 , 1580 and 1556 cm^{-1} respectively, but no bands are observed either at 1620 cm^{-1} , 1455 cm^{-1} and 1750 cm^{-1} . This large shift indicates strong coordination of both the carboxylate groups with the metal atom. Goulden⁵ has reported that in lactate ion the secondary alcoholic group has an in-plane bending absorption band at 1275 cm^{-1} which shifts to 1390 cm^{-1} on chelation with zinc. In sodium potassium tartrate, there is a band at about 1240 cm^{-1} which might be due to in-plane O-H bonding of secondary alcoholic groups. In these compounds, strong bands are observed at 1380 - 1375 cm^{-1} and weak bands at 1250 - 1260 cm^{-1} . These results indicate that one

TABLE 2

Compounds	Absorption band in cm^{-1}
$PbT \cdot OH$,	1560(s), 1375(s), 1125(m), 1075(m), 595(w), 510(w), 380
$PbT \cdot NH_3$,	1580(s), 1380(s), 1130(m), 1094(m), 590(w), 500(w), 400, 372
$PbTN(CH_3)_3$,	1556(s), 1375(s), 1125(m), 1070(m), 595(w), 505(w), 430, 390
Sodium Potassium tartrate	1620(s), 1455(w), 1240, 1110, 1060

of the alcoholic groups is bonded and the other is most probably free. In sodium potassium tartrate, two medium bands are formed at about 1110 and 1060 cm^{-1} which are probably due to C-O stretching of the two alcoholic groups. Corresponding bands in PbTOH_2 , PbT.NH_3 and $\text{PbTN}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ are respectively at 1125 and 1075 cm^{-1} , 1130 and 1094 cm^{-1} and 1125 and 1070 cm^{-1} . A little shift indicates chelation. Besides the above bands, lead(II) tartrate and its ammonia derivatives show strong and broad bands at 3480 cm^{-1} and 3270 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu\text{O}-\text{H}$ and $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ of water and ammonia molecule respectively. This shifting of the N-H stretching bands to lower frequency (free-ammonia 3420 cm^{-1}) is indicative of coordination through nitrogen. No definite assignments have been made for other vibrational frequencies of water or ammonia as they fall in the region of carboxylate and hydroxyl group frequencies of tartrate ligand. However, broad intensive bands in these regions may be attributed to the presence of coordinated water or ammonia (amine).

Metal-oxygen and metal-nitrogen bonds are generally found in the region below 750 cm^{-1} . In the study of copper(II) tartrate complexes⁹, the absorption bands in this region are so weak that it is difficult to characterise any distinct absorption bands in this region. In lead(II) tartrate derivatives lead atom being very heavy, the bands in this region though weak are very distinct.

The bands at 400 cm^{-1} in PbT.NH_3 and at 430 cm^{-1} in $\text{PbTN}(\text{CH}_3)_3$ are due to lead nitrogen bonds. The other bands found at 590-595 cm^{-1} , 500-510 cm^{-1} and 375-390 cm^{-1} are probably due to lead-oxygen bonds. It is therefore, very probable that Lead(II) is coordinated with two carboxylate groups and one of the two secondary alcoholic groups and a water or ammonia or amine molecule.

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Solid Phase Interaction Between Strontium Carbonate and Urea Nitrate

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IN an earlier communication a solid state interaction between dolomite and urea nitrate was reported from this laboratory¹. Strontium carbonate resembles calcium carbonate in all its properties and this prompted the author to investigate similar type of solid phase interaction between urea nitrate and strontium carbonate. The work consists of grinding strontium carbonate with urea nitrate in the mole ratio of 1 : 2 for an hour.

Experimental

1 g mole of strontium carbonate (A.R. BDH) was mixed with varying amounts of urea nitrate² and each mixture ground in an agate mortar for about an hour under dry conditions. In each case the resultant product was treated with distilled water (strontium carbonate insoluble) and filtered. In the filtrate, the amount of strontium nitrate was estimated³.

Results and Discussion

The results indicate that like dolomite-urea nitrate system¹ on grinding the mixture the protonation of strontium carbonate occurs resulting in the formation of strontium nitrate as one of the products which can be separated from insoluble strontium carbonate by dissolving the mixture in distilled water. The results reveal that with increasing urea nitrate content the percentage of water soluble strontium increases and at the stage of 1 : 2 mole ratio the solubility of the mixture becomes cent per cent. Further increase in the urea nitrate content does not give rise to increased amount of strontium nitrate in the filtrate. The limiting value of strontium nitrate found corresponds to one mole for every mole of strontium carbonate mixed with two moles of urea nitrate. Urea nitrate is an ionic salt while strontium carbonate is basic and probably on grinding the mixture an acid-base neutralization reaction occurs on account of an increase in the activation energy of the reaction

On grinding the mixture under dry conditions the textural and structural states of solid change and fresh surfaces of the reactants are exposed which enhances the rate of the chemical reaction. At the points of contact of the two solids protonation of the strontium carbonate occurs as a result of the